

Evaluation of the Efficacy of Aqueous and Alcoholic Extract of *Cinnamomum zeylanicum* Against the Growth of *Candida albicans* Isolated from Different Clinical Samples

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Abstract

This experiment was carried out in the laboratory of the Hussein Teaching Hospital in Karbala for the year 2020-2021 with the aim of studying the effect of the active compounds in the aqueous and alcoholic extract of cinnamon in inhibiting the growth of *Candida albicans* yeast. By GC-MS technique and also a qualitative detection of some active compounds in cinnamon bark, the results showed that cinnamon contains glycosides, tannins, resins, saponins and phenols. The aqueous and alcoholic extract showed a difference in the diameters of inhibition, where the highest inhibiting diameter reached (50 mg/ml) 32 mm and the lowest inhibition diameter was 25 mm, while the concentration (25 mg/ml) reached the highest inhibition diameter of 30 mm and the lowest inhibition diameter of 22 mm and concentration (12.5 mg/ml) the highest inhibition diameter reached 28 mm and the lowest inhibition diameter was 17 mm, while the concentration (6.25 mg/ml) reached the highest inhibition diameter 25 mm, and the minimum damping diameter is 12 mm.

Introduction

The therapeutic use of plants dates back to the Sumerian and Akkadian civilizations around the third millennium BC. Compounds of plant origin have been and continue to be an important source of pharmacological compounds as 3.4 billion people in the developing world depend on traditional botanical medicines. This represents about 88% of the world's population, who depend primarily on medicinal plants for their primary health care. According to the World Health Organization, a medicinal plant is any plant that contains in one or more of its organs substances that can be used for therapeutic purposes including leaves, roots, rhizomes, stems, bark, flowers, fruit, grains or seeds, used in the control or treatment of a diseased condition and thus contains Medicinally effective chemical components, therefore medicinal plants are the best source for obtaining a variety of medicines [1-4].

Secondary metabolites of medicinal plants are the basis of their therapeutic effects and are indicators of the quality of medicinal materials. The synthesis and

accumulation of these metabolites is affected by genetic and environmental factors such as light, temperature, and water. Medicinal and aromatic plants contain compounds such as phenols, flavonoids and alkaloids that act synergistically, enhancing their antioxidant and antifungal biological activity [5-7]. *Cinnamomum zeylanicum* belongs to the family Lauraceae. Cinnamon is a bark plant and is a dense tropical evergreen tree that can reach ten to forty meters in height. Cinnamon peels contain volatile oils, amounting to 4%, and the bark of this tree undergoes a drying process, which gives it the tubular shape [8]. The aroma and flavor of cinnamon derive from its essential oil and primary ingredient, cinnamaldehyde, as well as several other ingredients including eugenol [7]. The cinnamaldehyde in the cinnamon bark's essential oil is antibacterial, fungistatic and promotes motility. It has a mildly positive estrogen effect on the genital system of animals in tests, although the constituent responsible is unidentified. Cinnamon increases gastric secretions slightly and is an insecticide due to the diterpenes cinnzeylanin and cinnceylanol

More Information

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Cinnamomum zeylanicum, *Candida albicans*, GC-MS, antifungal activity.

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[9].

Cinnamon has multiple health benefits, as it is used to treat nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, and muscle pain. It also helps increase the secretion of saliva and gastric juices, lowers blood pressure, and stimulates the appetite. It contains a phenolic substance that makes fat cells more responsive to insulin, which regulates the breakdown of sugar in the blood and converts it into energy. This phenolic substance has antioxidant properties, which leads to reducing the effects of diabetes. It also has biological properties that are antifungal and antibacterial and protect against colon disorders. It contains many Antioxidant compounds. [10].

The fragrance of cinnamon is due to the essential oils, which are 0.5-1% of its components. These oils are golden yellow in color, which gives cinnamon a distinctive smell and sharp taste. Chemical compounds of oils include. Eugenol, ethyl cinnamate, cinnamaldehyde, B-caryophylline, linalool (methylchavicol) volatile oil: chief components - cinnamaldehyde, weiterhin eugenol, cinnamylacetate, cinnamyl alcohol, o-methoxycinnamaldehyde, cinnamic. Diterpenes: cinnzeylanol, cinnzeylanin Oligomeric proanthocyanidins Mucilages [11-13].

Candida albicans is a yeast found in the human body, settling in various parts of the body such as the mucous surfaces of the mouth, the digestive tract, and the urinary and reproductive tracts. It can turn into a pathogenic microbe that causes serious diseases, especially in immunocompromised people. It is characterized by its ability to adapt to the environment and change its growth form. Temperature and pH greatly affect it. Its cells are surrounded by a multilayered cell wall and a cell membrane containing lipids and proteins. Enzymes needed to build the wall are secreted, and the cell membrane is a target for antifungal antibiotics [14].

Most of the biological functions related to virulence or disease return to the cell wall, which is the place of contact between the cell and the surrounding environment. *Candida albicans* cells contain twice as much chitin than the yeast wall [15]. The pathogenesis of *Candida albicans* is due to a combination of virulence factors such as biofilm formation and secretion of hydrolytic enzymes (including phospholipase and proteinase). The enzyme phospholipase causes the hydrolysis of phospholipids in host cell membranes causing membrane disintegration and facilitating penetration and cell invasion [16,17].

There are also a group of factors that affect the host, for example, cases of weak immune system, as these yeasts analyze the host tissues for the purpose of helping the yeast in invading the tissues and avoiding the immune cells that affect the site of infection, and therefore the yeast succeeds in infecting this site and

this genus It has the ability to form filaments that stick to the host cells and penetrate the epithelial cells of the surface, facilitating infection [18-20].

Several types of antifungals are used to treat fungal infections, including azoles, polyenes, and echinocandins. These drugs target different biochemical pathways unique to yeast. Azoles target the biosynthesis of ergosterol, a component of the cell membrane found only in fungi. The effectiveness of these antifungals depends on the quality of the host's immune system, the severity of the infection, and the pharmacokinetics of the drugs [21].

Some *Candida* species have shown high levels of resistance to antifungals and these species have shown resistance patterns to drugs such as nystatin, clotrimazole, fluconazole, itraconazole, and amphotericin. The emergence of multidrug resistance in human pathogenic fungi and the limited number of available antifungal drug classes have stimulated research directed towards the discovery of new antifungal agents from other sources, such as medicinal plants. The world is now turning to alternatives to these antibiotics as antifungals, represented by natural products extracted from many plants because they contain active substances [22,23].

Pathological microorganisms, which it is possible to conduct research and experiments on these plants, so the current study was conducted to know the inhibitory effect of cinnamon aqueous extract against *Candida albicans* yeast.

Materials and Methods

Collection of Plant Samples

Cinnamon bark samples were collected from the local markets in Karbala governorate, the required parts were washed with normal water, then with distilled water, dried in the shade, then ground with an electric mill, and the dry powders were kept in opaque sealed containers until use.

Preparation of Aqueous and Alcoholic Extracts

50 g of dry plant powder for each of the plant samples was weighed and mixed with 500 ml of 70% ethyl alcohol in a 1000 ml glass beaker, closed with cotton and aluminum foil, placed in a vibrating incubator and left for 24 hours at room temperature, then the mixture was filtered using several layers of medical gauze for disposal The plankton was then centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes, and the extract was filtered using 0.1 Whatman NO filter papers. To obtain a clear solution, then dry the extract using the oven at a temperature of 40 °C, then keep the extract in an opaque flask in the refrigerator until use. Prepare the aqueous extract in the same way, replacing the alcohol with distil water [24].

Qualitative and Quantitative Analysis

Qualitative and quantitative analysis of chemical compounds in plant samples using the GC-MS

technique Determination of leaf content of active substances using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry.

Active Compound Diagnostics

Components were identified using the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) database by comparing the resulting spectrum of the unknown component with known stored components in the NIST library. This analysis was carried out at the Mass Spectrometry Gas Chromatography Laboratory in the Environment and Water Department of the Ministry of Science and Technology.

Qualitative statements: A set of qualitative statements was made to identify the chemical components in the hot alcoholic extract of the plants:

1) Alkaloid test: Alkaloids were detected using the following reagents:

A. Dragendorff Reagent [25]: Several drops of the reagent were added to (1) ml of the extract, when an orange precipitate appears, the result is positive, which indicates the presence of alkaloids.

B. Wagner's Reagent [26]: Several drops of the reagent were added to (1) ml of the extract, when turbidity appears, the result is positive, which indicates the presence of alkaloids.

2) Detection of flavonoids test [27]: 1 ml of the reagent (Ethanol KOH [5N]) was added to 1 ml of the extract, when a yellow precipitate appears, the result is positive, which indicates the presence of flavonoids.

3) Detection of tannins test [27]: Add 1 ml of aqueous lead acetate (1%) to 1 ml of the extract, when a white precipitate is formed, the result is positive, which indicates the presence of tannins.

4) Phenol's test [27]: Dissolve 0.1 g of the extract in 1 ml of distilled water and add 1-2 drops of FeCl₃ (1%) ferric chloride solution, when blue or green color appears, the result is positive, which indicates the presence of phenols.

5) Saponin test [27]: Add 1 ml of aqueous mercury chloride reagent (5%) to 1 ml of the extract, when a white precipitate is formed, the result is positive, which indicates the presence of saponins.

The Isolates Used

90 samples were collected from different clinical cases and included (26) oral samples, (21) samples from sputum, (11) samples from wound swabs, (13) samples from skin swabs and (19) urine swab for people with different fungal infections and for both Both sexes and different ages for the period of time from 1/12/2020 - 30/4/2021 from the Hussein Teaching Hospital in the Holy Karbala Governorate Samples were planted on SDA medium, and the dishes were incubated at 37°C for 24 - 48 hours.

Isolation and Identification

Direct Microscopic Examination of Yeast Samples

The examination was carried out using the [28,29] method.

Germ Tube Formation

The examination was carried out using the [30] method. Germ tube formation test was conducted to distinguish between species belonging to the genus spp. *Candida*, characterized by *C. albicans* and *dubliniensis* yeasts. by its composition, the germ tube, and it is in the form of a long extension from the surface of the yeast cell, and the base of its attachment to the cell is wide, and it can be distinguished from the pseudo hyphae, which have a narrow point of connection.

Tobacco Agar Media

50 g of tobacco was used, it was boiled for 30 minutes, then it was filtered by several layers of gauze. The filtrate was collected and added to it 20 gm of agar and 50 mg of the antibiotic chloramphenicol and completed the volume to 1000 ml of distilled water and sterilized the purifier. Pour the medium into sterile Petri dishes and kept in the refrigerator until use. This medium was used to differentiate between the two species *C. albicans* and *dubliniensis*. Depending on the morphological characteristics of the fungus (35), yeast samples were plotted on the surface of the prepared medium and incubated at a temperature of 28° C. The growth was monitored for 1-4 days, where clear phenotypic differences appeared in the growing farms, such as the nature of the surface rough or smooth and the color of the developing colonies) [31].

Agar Black Tea Media

This media was used to investigate the species producing chlamydial spores. 50 gm of dried tea leaves were placed in 1000 ml of distilled water, boiled for 15 minutes, then filtered with filter papers, 20 gm of agar was added to it and sterilized with oxidizer for 20 minutes, then the medium was poured into Petri dishes and left to cool, and part of the candida colony was cultured, where the surface of the medium was planned and covered with a sterile glass slide cover. The dishes were incubated at a temperature of 28 ° C for 72-48 hours. The glass slide was examined to see chlamydial spores and pseudo-hyphae, if found, under a microscope with a force of 40X.

The Growing at 45°C

This test was conducted according to the method [32] by plotting the samples on SDA medium, then incubated at a temperature of 45 °C. Growth was monitored for 10 days, as only *C. albicans* can grow at this high temperature.

Determination of the Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)

Determination of the Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) of the aqueous extract of *Cinnamomum zeylanicum* The Broth Dilution Technique

described by [33], which depends on the turbidity of yeast growth, was followed in preparing a series of half-dilutions of the surface biodispersion for the purpose of determining the MIC, as follows: 8 tubes numbered 1-8 were used and 1 ml of Nutrient Broth liquid broth was added and sterilized at 121 ° C for 15 minutes, a stock solution was prepared for both aqueous and alcoholic extract of cinnamon, 0.1 mg of it was dissolved in 1 ml of solution Phosphate-Saline buffer PBS To obtain a final concentration of 100 mg/ml, a series of half-dilutions (50, 25, 12.5, 6.25, 3.12, 1.56) mg/ml for each aqueous and alcoholic extract of cinnamon were prepared by adding 1 ml to the first tube and shake well, then 1 ml was transferred from the first tube to the second tube and shaken well, then 1 ml was transferred from the second tube to the third tube and the process was repeated all the way to tube No. 6 when it was shaken and 1 ml was removed from it to get a final volume of 1 ml in each tube and changed Pipette between tubes to prevent contamination. Tubes No. 7 and 8 were left without adding any substance. Yeast inoculum was prepared by transferring pure single colonies of yeast to a tube containing 5 ml of physiological saline and its turbidity was compared with the turbidity of MacFarland tubes. 0.1 ml of the yeast suspension prepared in the previous step was transferred to tubes 1-7 and tube No. 8 was left without addition. Tubes No. 7 and 8 were considered positive and negative control tubes, the first containing the culture medium and the yeast suspension, and the second on the culture medium only. The tubes were incubated at 37 ° C for 24 hours, and after the incubation period, the tubes were checked for the presence or absence of turbidity.

The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was determined after incubation, which represents the lowest concentration of the surface biodispersion in which no visible yeast growth was observed. Nutrient agar medium, plates were incubated at 37° C for 24 hours and after incubation growth was observed [34].

The Plant Extract Efficacy Test [35]

The isolates under study were activated in the nutrient medium, prepared according to the instructions of the supplied company. Solidification The medium was inoculated with the suspension, the fungal suspension was spread using sterile cotton swabs. The dishes were left for 15 minutes to imbibe the suspension in the culture medium, then 5 holes were made in each dish with a diameter of 7 mm using a sterile cork piercing and 10 microliters were added to each of the alcoholic and aqueous extract at a concentration of 50% mg/ ml, 25%, 12.5%, 6.25% each concentration in a pit using a micropipette. The dishes were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours, then the results were recorded by measuring the diameters of the damping area in mm.

Statistical analysis was performed using GenStat software.

Results and Discussion

The results of the qualitative detection of the active groups in cinnamon extract Table (1) showed that they contain glycosides, tannins, resins, saponins, phenols and pH 6,3. These results are in agreement with what was mentioned by the researchers [35], who confirmed that cinnamon contains the above-mentioned compounds in varying proportions. The cold aqueous extract of cinnamon contained all of the active compound's glycosides, tannins, resins, saponins, and phenols. The presence of terpenes, alkaloids and steroids was not observed.

Table 1: Qualitative Detection of Some Active Groups of Alcoholic Extract

Active groups	alcoholic extract
Glycosides	+
Alkaloids	-
Tannins	+++
resins	+
Soaps	+++
flavones	-
Phenols	++
turbines	-
steroids	-
pH	6

Table (2) shows the chemical compounds present in the alcoholic extract of the bark of the cinnamon plant *Cinnamomum zeylanicum*, which was detected using gas chromatography technology equipped with mass spectrometry, as the detection showed There are 29 compounds in the cinnamon plant, and the highest peak area of the cinnamon extract was 7.98 minutes for the compound Cinnamaldehyde. The lowest peak area was 6.19 minutes for 3-Phenylpropanol, Cinnamaldehyde is a natural phenolic compound that belongs to the aldehydes group. It is the compound responsible for giving cinnamon its distinctive aroma and flavour. It is found naturally in cinnamon bark. It has strong antimicrobial effects and has been approved by the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and the European Council for use in food products [36].

This compound has a biological activity that inhibits fungal growth by impairing ergosterol biosynthesis and cell membrane function, causing damage to the yeast cell membrane and mycotoxin production[37,38].

In a study by [39], cinnamaldehyde shows antifungal activity by inhibiting germ tube formation, adhesion to epithelial cells and secretion of the hydrolytic enzyme pathogenic *C. albicans* and inhibition of these virulence factors by cinnamaldehyde may be useful in the treatment of candidiasis.

Table2: GC-MS. Analysis of Alcoholic Extract of *Cinnamomum zeylanicum*

Compound name	Real time	Aera %	Molecular Formula	Structure Formula
3-phenyl-, acetate	17.33	2.66	C₁₁H₁₂O₂	
trans-cinnamaldehyde,	8.29	2.76	C₉H₈O	
gamma. Terpineol	10.45	0.87	C₁₀H₁₈O	
muurolene,α	17.46	0.90	C₁₅H₂₄	
9-Octadecenamide	11.58	2.76	C₁₈H₃₅NO	
Copaene	13.63	1.65	C₁₅H₂₄	
coumarin	4.96	0.87	C₉H₆O₂	
Cyclohexene-1-methanol	11.73	1.06	C₇H₁₂O	
6-Oxa-bicyclo [3.1.0]	3.12	2.69	C₅H₈O	
Mandelic acid	9.87	1.69	C₈H₈O₃	
caryophyllene	5.38	0.78	C₁₅H₂₄	
2-Propen- 1- ol,	7.69	0.58	C₃H₄O	
(E)-3-Phenylpropenal	9.57	0.95	C₉H₈O	
4-terpineol,	3.78	1.54	C₁₀H₁₈O	

3-Phenylpropanol	6.19	1.30	C₉H₁₂O	
Cinnamic alcohol	4.98	1.7	C₉H₁₀O	
_terpinene α	10.78	1.45	C₁₀H₁₆	
Benzaldehyde	2.96	0.94	C₇H₆O	
Cinnamaldehyde	7.98	50.78	C₉H₈O	
1,8-cineole,	18.59	1.76	C₁₀H₁₈O	
camphenilol,	16.94	0.98	C₈H₁₄O	
camphene	3.84	1.95	C₁₀H₁₆	
β-Guaiene	9.85	2.87	C₁₅H₂₄	
β, pinene	6.29	1.54	C₁₀H₁₆	
Cubanol	12.80	3.78	C₁₅H₂₆O	
α, pinene	14.37	3.21	C₁₀H₁₆	
Stigmasterol	20.84	2.12	C₂₉H₄₈O	
borneol,	9.78	1.11	C₁₀H₁₈O	
cyclohexane	3.49	1.45	C₆H₁₂	

Tau-Muurolol	10.84	1.65	C₁₅H₂₆O	
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Numbers and percentages for isolating pathogenic candida species

31 isolates were diagnosed, with a percentage of 34% being isolated from the total samples, 90 samples Table (3), where clinical samples included mouth, sputum, wounds, skin and urine were isolated in different proportions, respectively (34.6%, 38.1%, 45.4%, 23.1% and 31.5%) and the infection rates varied as The highest percentage of wound samples was 45.4% and the lowest percentage of skin swabs reached 23.1%. The reason for the occurrence of infection with these yeasts is due to their presence and widespread spread in the environment and their possession of some virulence factors that enable them to cause infection and produce massive reproductive units [40,41]. The difference in isolation rates in this study could be due to the difference in antibiotic policies in different hospitals, as incorrect use of antibiotics suppresses the normal flora making patients susceptible to developing immunity to Candida [42].

Candida possesses many virulence factors, such as adhesion to surfaces and host cells, secretion of hydrolytic enzymes, Biofilm Formation, evasion of the host immune response, and thermal tolerance. All of these factors collectively contribute to Candida pathogenicity, enabling it to colonize, invade, and cause infection in the host [43-45].

Table 3: Numbers and Percentages of Isolated Pathological Types of Candida

Clinical samples	The number of samples tested	Positive	percentage
mouth	26	9	34.6%
cough	21	8	38.1%
wounds	11	5	45.4%
skine	13	3	23.1%
urine	19	6	31.5
Total number	90	31	

Diagnosis

Cultural Characteristics

Figure (1) shows growing colonies appeared on the medium of saproid dextrose agar SDA in the form of white to cream-coloured, smooth, and circular colonies. In this regard [46], indicates that the colonies of Candida spp. It possesses such phenotypical characteristics when cultured on the aforementioned medium, and this result agrees with what was mentioned by [34] with the appearance of colonies

with a creamy, glossy color, smooth and circular in shape, to provide the appropriate culture conditions.

Figure 1: Growing Colonies of Candida albicans

Germ Tube Formation

Figure (2) showed the test results that all isolates belonging to the type *C. albicans* formed germ tubes when incubated at a temperature of 37 °C for a period of 2-3 hours in 0.5 ml of human blood serum, but all other species *C. tropicalis*, *C. parapsilosis*, *C. krusei* did not. The germ tube is formed under the same conditions, and these results are consistent with [35], whose study results showed that only *C. albicans* has the ability to form the germ tube in this test and in the presence of the catalyst (serum) that works to form it around the yeast cell, and that the germ tube plays an important role In the process of penetrating the layer of epithelial cells lining the body and tissues and reaching the bloodstream as well as it is believed to be necessary to feed the yeast [47].

Figure 2: The Formation of the Germ Tube in Yeast Chlamydia Spores' Formation

The results of this test showed that all the isolates belonging to the type *C.albicans* formed chlamydial spores, while the other species did not form it under the same conditions (25 m for a period of 24 hours). The result of this examination was identical to the result of [48], since The results of the study showed that the type *C.albicans* formed chlamydial spores on corn meal agar medium, as this medium is a diagnostic characteristic of the type *C.albicans*. The spores with thick walls, circular in shape, formed at the end of the hypha hyphae, which may be single or clustered in clusters when cultured on a medium. (CMA) as a result of starvation of yeasts due to a shortage of food sources, as they are formed when conditions are not suitable for them, as this medium is described as the medium of starving yeasts.

Growth at a Temperature of 45 °C

This test was used to differentiate between the type *C. albicans* and the rest of the other types of yeasts, so the results showed that only the type *C. albicans* can grow to this degree, while the other types were not able to grow in the same conditions, and this is consistent with [49], where the results of the study showed that

isolates of *C. parapsilosis*. It is unable to grow at a temperature of 45 degrees. As for the type *C.albicans*, it can grow at that degree. The reason for *C.albicans* tolerance of growth at 45 degrees Celsius is due to genetic factors linked to the genes of virulence factors, including its ability to form chlamydial spores capable of resisting harmful external influences.

Determine the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC)

We note from the results of Table (4) that the value of the minimum inhibitory concentration of the aqueous extract of the cinnamon plant was 6.25 mg/ml for the yeast isolates used in the study, and that the effect of this extract depends on the concentration used and its containment of active substances. The difference in the sensitivity of the fungus to the extract may be due to the nature of the fungus itself in terms of its cellular structure, cell wall thickness, fat and protein content of the fungus, and it may also be due to the mechanism and effectiveness of the active components of the plant extract that may change the shape and structure of membranes. fungal cells [50].

Table 4: Determination of the Minimal Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)

Concent	%1.56	%3.12	%6.25	%12.5	%25	%50
Mouth	-	-	+	+	+	+
Cough	-	-	+	+	+	+
Wound	-	-	+	+	+	+
Skin	-	-	+	+	+	+
Urine	-	-	+	+	+	+

The results of Table (5) show that the concentration of 50 mg / ml of the aqueous extract of cinnamon is more effective in the inhibition diameters compared to the control coefficient, where the average inhibition diameter was 29.40 mm, and that the concentration of

6.25 mg / ml had less effect on the inhibition diameters, as the average inhibition diameter was 19.27 mm compared to Control factor containing sterile distilled water.

Table 5: Diameters of Inhibition Zones (mm) for Different Concentrations of Cold Aqueous Extract of *Cinnamomum zeylanicum* against the Growth of *Candida albicans*

Concen.	Cont.	6.25mg	12.5mg	25mg	50mg	Average
sample						
Cough	0	21.67	25.33	26.67	30.33	20.80
Urine	0	12.00	17.33	21.67	24.67	15.13
Mouth	0	17.00	18.33	26.33	28.00	17.93
Skin	0	24.67	27.67	30.00	33.00	23.07
Wound	0	21.00	24.00	31.67	13.00	21.53
Average	0	19.27	22.53	27.27	29.40	
L.S.D	S.0.904	C.0.904	S*C2.022			

The results of Table (6) show that the concentration of 50 mg / ml of the alcoholic extract of cinnamon is more effective in the average inhibition diameter compared to the control coefficient, where the average inhibition diameter was 19.60 mm, and the concentration of 6.25

mg / ml had less effect on the inhibition diameter, as the average inhibition diameter was 8.40 mm Compared to the control coefficient containing sterile distilled water

Table 6: Inhibition Zone Diameters (mm) for Different Concentrations of Alcoholic Extract of *Cinnamomum zeylanicum* against the Growth of *Candida albicans*

Conce. sample	Cont.	6.25mg	12.5mg	25mg	50mg	Average
Cough	0	11.67	13.67	16.00	20.00	12.27
Urine	0	2.00	7.00	11.67	15.00	7.13
Mouth	0	7.00	8.33	14.67	18.00	9.60
Skin	0	10.67	17.33	19.67	21.00	13.73
Wound	0	10.67	15.00	21.00	24.00	14.13
Average	0	8.40	12.27	16.60	19.60	
L.S.D	S.0.892	C.0.892	S*C.1.995			

It is clear from the above results that the best rate of inhibition diameter was in favor of the concentration of 50 mg/ml. The increase in the diameter of the inhibition zones compared to an increase in the concentration is due to the extract of the cinnamon plant having inhibitory activity against pathogenic yeasts, and the inhibitory effect of the surface bio scatter can be attributed to the substances it contains. discouraging. The anti-efficacy of the extract of the cinnamon plant increases with increasing its concentration, and this is due to the fact that it contains inhibitory compounds that have a role in inhibiting the growth of yeasts due to the effect of active groups such as glycosides, phenols, resins, and saponins, which may make it have a higher inhibitory effectiveness, and this is consistent [50]. The reason for the ability of the extract to inhibit the growth of yeasts may be due to the fact that it contains some phenolic compounds, such as thymol, which has inhibitory activity against yeasts, which has an effect on the cell wall by dissolving cell wall fats and forming hydrogen bonds with water molecules and nitrogen of amino acids inside the cell, which affects the mechanism of the work of the cell membrane of the living and thus inhibiting the growth of the microorganism. This indicates the biological effect of the extract of cinnamon, which led to an imbalance in the activity of fungal cells, preventing them from multiplying, dividing and growing, such as affecting the permeability of the cell membrane as a result of inhibiting the process of manufacturing cellular proteins that are part of the formation of the cell wall and the cell membrane. Proteins necessary for the cell and involved in its construction and activity, such as enzymes necessary to regulate and sustain cellular activities and control divisions [51]. Several researchers have indicated a relationship between chemical structure and antifungal activity. They also showed that the strong antifungal efficacy of oils derived from bark and cinnamon leaf was due to higher levels of cinnamaldehyde (44.2%) and eugenol (90.2%) However, other compounds may also contribute to antifungal activity [52].

Conclusions

The results of this study showed the presence of 29 compounds in the alcoholic extract of the bark of the cinnamon plant, *Cinnamomum zeylanicum*. These compounds were identified through GC-MS technology, and that the aqueous extract had a noticeable inhibitory activity against pathogenic yeasts that increased with increasing concentration. This is due to the presence of effective compounds such as glycosides, phenols, volatile oils, and resins. These results indicate that this extract may be useful in treating candidiasis

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